

LANGUAGE AND CULTURE IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS: GREETINGS, WAYS OF EXPRESSING POLITENESS

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Abstract: This article looks at how casual and slang greetings are used in English classes, with an emphasis on the effects these non-formal forms of communication have on student-teacher interactions and classroom dynamics. The study investigates how common slang and informal greetings are among students and how this affects their sociolinguistic competence and language ability. The study examines the possible problems that colloquialisms and informal welcomes may have for formal language training in addition to their usefulness in fostering a laid-back and welcoming learning atmosphere. This study looks into how slang and informal greetings are used in English classes in an effort to provide light on the intricate interactions that occur between language, culture, and classroom communication.

Key words: Slang greetings, casual greetings, TESOL, English classroom, teaching culture, and greetings.

Introduction. Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) includes teaching culture as a core component. Students who want to communicate successfully in English need to be aware of the vocabulary, grammar, functions, and proper times and body language for each of these elements. While grammar and vocabulary make up the majority of any language, cultural awareness ties these elements together and facilitates communication for students. Language and culture are vital in the classroom. If this part of language is neglected, it may negatively impact the student's capacity for successful communication. English culture is derived from the cultures of English-speaking nations such as the United States and Great Britain. Johnson (2009) asserts that a person cannot acquire a language without embracing the culture that goes along with it. As a result, learning the language forces a person to embrace its cultures. Learning about many cultures in school helps students feel safer and more at ease with these differences in the future. As a result, they are able to engage with a greater variety of social groups and experience an increase in self-assurance and interpersonal confidence.

The enduring social realities that develop in a classroom, such as customs and habits, are known as classroom culture. For instance, classroom culture is the widespread inclination of the group to either follow or disregard the guideline of classroom management.

A specific language can reveal information about a social group's culture. Thus, learning a language involves more than just mastering its alphabet, grammatical rules, and word order; it also entails knowing the cultural norms and behavior of the community. Deeper down, language is a reflection of our identities as people, groups, and countries. Culture encompasses dynamic social structures as well as common patterns of conduct, attitudes, knowledge, beliefs, and values.

Understanding culture is essential to learning English since it enables one to think in a different language. The phrases won't need to be written in your original tongue and then translated into the target language. Knowing the culture enables you to think in the foreign language and provide the appropriate meaning to each word in the context. It serves a significant social role in fostering a sense of collective identification and cohesion by serving as a vehicle for the communication of values, beliefs, and practices. It is a way to transmit and maintain culture, along with its customs and common values. The foundation of cultural identity is language. What connection exists between English language and culture?

Both of them are entangled. A distinct language typically targets a particular demographic. Interacting with someone who speaks a different language also entails interacting with their culture. Without having direct access to the language of that culture, one cannot comprehend it.

English greetings that go beyond "Hello" and "How Are You?" In English, "hello" and "how are you?" are presumably already familiar to you. To say somewhat different things, English speakers also employ a wide variety of additional English greetings and idioms. Together with some entertaining slang terms that English speakers use to greet one another, let's learn how to utilize some additional basic formal and casual welcomes in English.

In most business settings, it's ideal to start with formal welcomes and then observe how your colleagues or business partners greet you. It's a good idea to hold off on having casual conversations with someone until you've had some casual conversations with them. As you get to know one another better, you could notice that individuals start extending informal greetings to you.

When addressing senior citizens, you should also utilize formal greetings.

1. How do you do?

This greeting is VERY formal, and quite uncommon and old-fashioned now, but it may still be used by some older people.

The proper response is "I'm doing well" or, as strange as it seems, some people even ask "how do you do?" right back as an answer.

Informal Greetings in English.

2. Hey, Hey man or Hi.

You can use "hey" and "hi" to greet someone instead of "hello." Both are particularly popular among younger people.

While "hi" is appropriate to use in any casual situation, "hey" is for people who have already met. If you say "hey" to a stranger, it might be confusing for that person because he or she will try to remember when you met before!

You can also add "man" to the end of "hey" when greeting males. Some people also use "hey man" to casually greet younger women, but only do this if you know the woman very well. Remember that "hey" doesn't always mean "hello." "Hey" can also be used to call for someone's attention.

3. How have you been?

This greeting question is only asked by people who have already met. If someone asks you "how have you been?" they want to know if you have been well since the last time the two of you met.

4. Good morning, Good afternoon or Good evening.

These are formal ways of saying “hello”, which change depending on the time of day.

Keep in mind that “good night” is only used to say “goodbye,” so if you meet someone late in the day, remember to greet them with “good evening,” rather than “good night.”

“Good morning” can be made more casual by simply saying “morning.” You can also simply use “afternoon” or “evening” as informal greetings, but these are less commonly used.

5. It’s nice to meet you or Pleased to meet you.

These greetings are formal and polite. If you say this to someone when you meet him or her for the first time, it will make you seem courteous (polite).

Remember to only use these greetings the first time you meet someone. Next time you see the person you can show that you remember him or her by saying “it’s nice to see you again” or simply “it’s nice to see you.”

6. Greeting a stranger.

But what about introducing yourself to a stranger?

Speaking with strangers is often a dreaded (feared) task for many speaking in a second language, and for English learners it is no different. We have particular titles used for greeting strangers in English and usually, it is more formal speech.

7. How’s your day? or How’s your day going?

These questions mean “how are you?” not just right now, but how you’ve been all day. You would use these greetings later in the day and with someone you see regularly.

For example, you might ask a co-worker one of these in the afternoon, or a cashier that you see at the grocery store every evening.

“It’s going well” is the grammatically correct response, but many people simply answer with “fine,” “good” or “alright.”

By the way, notice that “good,” “fine” or “not bad” are perfect answers to almost any greeting question.

8. How’s everything?, How are things? or How’s life?

These can be used to casually greet someone and ask how the person is doing, but most often these sentences are used to greet someone you already know. To these, you can answer “good” or “not bad.”

Again, if small talk feels appropriate, you could also briefly share any interesting news about your life, and then ask the person “what about you?” or another greeting question.

9. What’s up?, What’s new? or What’s going on?

These are some other informal ways of asking “how are you?” which are typically used to casually greet someone you have met before. Most people answer with “nothing” or “not much.”

Or, if it feels right to make small talk, you could also briefly describe anything new or interesting that’s going on in your life, before asking “what about you?” to continue the conversation.

10. How’s it going? or How are you doing?

These are casual ways of asking “how are you?” If you’re trying to be particularly polite, stick with “how are you?” but otherwise, you can use these expressions to greet almost anyone.

The word “going” is usually shortened, so it sounds more like “go-in”. You can answer with “it’s going well” or “I’m doing well” depending on the question.

Although it's not grammatically correct, most people just answer "good"—and you can too. Like when responding to "how are you?" you can also follow your answer by asking "and you?"

11. Yo!

This extremely informal greeting is common in the U.S. It comes from 1990's hip-hop slang and these days it's often used both seriously and jokingly.

This greeting should only be used with very close friends, and never in a business setting.

12. Howdy! This is a very informal abbreviation of "how do you do?" that is common in certain parts of Canada and the U.S.

Keep in mind that if you say "howdy" outside of these regions, you will sound like a cowboy, and it might make the other person laugh.

This greeting, short for "how are you?", is commonly used in certain parts of England. However, you don't need to actually answer this question—you can just say "hey!" right back. And of course, once you've nailed the introductions, there's another set of phrases you need to learn. That's right, farewells (saying goodbye)! This video will give you a brief introduction to saying goodbye in English. I hope you enjoy trying out these new English greetings. You'll find that greeting people in different ways will help your English sound more natural, and it might even make English greetings more fun and interesting for you.

13. Long time no see or It's been a while.

These casual greetings are used when you haven't seen someone in a long time, particularly if you meet that person unexpectedly.

How much is a long time? It depends on how often you normally see that person. For example, you could use one of these greetings if you normally see the person every week, but then don't see them for a few months or more.

Usually, these phrases are followed by another question, like "how are you," "how have you been?" or "what's new?"

Slang Greetings in English.

Slang greetings are extremely informal, and should only be used with people that you know very well, and feel very comfortable with.

Keep in mind that a lot of slang is regional, and using Australian slang in the United States, for example, can sound quite strange.

You'll need to learn the local slang wherever you are, but these common examples will help you get started.

14. Good to see you or Nice to see you.

These casual greetings are used with friends, co-workers or family members that you haven't seen in a while.

It's common for close friends to hug when they greet each other, particularly if they haven't seen each other in some time. So you might use this greeting along with a hug or handshake depending on your relationship with the person.

15. Are you OK?, You alright? or Alright mate?

This casual way of asking both "hello" and "how are you" is common in Britain.

You can respond "yeah, fine," or simply "alright" before asking "and you?" to the other person.

In conclusion, welcomes and introductions differ throughout English-speaking nations and cultures, yet they are all crucial components of everyday discourse. In many nations,

especially in professional contexts, greetings with a handshake are customary; but, in less formal circumstances, gestures like a wave, a nod, or an embrace could be more suitable. In addition to giving one's first and last names when introducing oneself, it is also common in various cultures to mention one's occupation or work title.

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